

EPITHETS AS A POETIC IDENTIFIER (IN THE EXAMPLE OF THE "SUTRA OF GOLDEN LIGHT")

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4713531>

ARTICLE INFO

ed: 15th April 2021
Accepted: 19th April 2021
Online: 21st April 2021

KEY WORDS

epithet, expressive mean, Buddha, tautological epithets, poetic function, artistic identifier.

ABSTRACT

The paper reveals structural and semantic peculiarities of the epithet. The research material is represented with epithets from "Oltun yorug" ("Sutra of Golden light"). The semantic potential of the epithet, in our opinion, did not receive a proper description in linguopoetics, which focuses exclusively on comparison within the framework of this construction. An attempt is made on the material of the Buddhist Sutra "Oltin Yorug" show the central role of the epithet in figurative understanding of reality. The article provides an overview of papers written by Russian philologists who examined epithet problems.

Religions play an important role in human development, spiritual and enlightenment perfection. In this regard, it should be noted that "the East has long been the cradle of the spiritual process." When Islam entered the Central Asia, the peoples of the region chose Islam as the path to the Truth, but even before Islam, there were religions such as Monism, Shamanism, Zoroastrianism, Tengerism, Buddhism, Christianity. Among them, "Buddhism had a special place in the life of the peoples of East Turkestan in the first centuries AD and the Middle Ages." The work of „Oltin Yorug“ is one of the most remarkable sources of this movement and has served to stabilize the spiritual environment of the Turkic-speaking peoples of Central Asia.

After the translation of the text of this work into Uzbek by Professor Nasimhon Rahmon, the study of the text of the work, the means of

poetic actualization of language became one of the tasks of researchers. Since Buddhism is a unique tradition, the definition of epithets and their poetic function in the text is a priority in research.

An epithet (from the ancient Greek ἐπίθετον - "attached") is a means of influencing the beautiful expression and pronunciation of a word. In syntax they are like identifiers, in etymology they are adjectives, but they have their own characteristics. The term "epithet" is one of the oldest philological terms used to describe the expressive means used by authors of literary texts. The most surprising aspect is that the term is a unit of existing meaning: since ancient rhetoric, an epithet has been understood as an expressive description describing an object or event. However, in philological traditions dating back to antiquity, the separation of the two epithets which are "necessary epithets" (epitheton

necessarium, providing information on a topic not otherwise provided in the text) and "decorative epithets" (epitheton ornans, which does not imply new subject-logical information, but only affects the emotions of the students) has become a habit.

It should be noted that the name of the founder of Buddhism - "Buddha" is also an epithet. The word "Buddha" is derived from Sanskrit, and the root "budh" means awakening, the transition from a dormant, darkened consciousness to an awakening, an enlightened consciousness.

There is no definite rule in the classification of epithets in literary theory, they are known as speech figures, parts of tropes, and some as a separate artistic poetic medium. The main function of epithets is to embellish the language, to bring high art and beauty to the word. Citing a permanent feature of a character is not an epithet, specific characters created in the author's imagination or after an in-depth analysis can be epithets. For example, the phrase "flood river" cannot be taken as an epithet, because flood is a constant quality inherent in a river.

"Pooring into from the poor for knowledge"

The phrase "the poor" in this passage has a very subtle meaning and is the result of the author's honest analysis and evaluation.

Epithets are not only the product of the author's lofty thinking or imagination, they can also harden and change over the years, as exemplified by more and more folk oral epithets. Epithets, their history and classification were studied by the famous Russian scientist AN Veselovsky. According to the scientist, the epithet "... is a one-sided definition of the word, or renewing the meaning of its common name" or strengthening, emphasizing some specific,

recognizable quality of the object. " In this case, the scientist classifies epithets into two groups, the first of which is a tautological epithet - essentially specific words, both adjectives and nouns are similar and mean the same idea, brilliance. Often, the second word returns the base of the first word.

Common tautological epithets in "Oltin yorug": t(ä)ngri t(ä)ngri (god of gods), tip tisün (let smb say), yidin yiparin (fragrant smells), ötünmish ötügümin (cry).

Repetition of a set of root words of a certain quality cannot always be an epithet, in which some poetic function is hidden.

Shklovsky, a representative of the Russian formal school, accepted Veselovsky's postulate and said: "Art and word live, are stoned, and die. And the tongue is like a graveyard. Only by giving them a new meaning can they be revived, developed.

Let's look for an example of these ideas in "Oltin yorug":

VIII. 35b

äriti y(ä)mä qilmaghu ol nomsuz törüsüz qiliqigh

(let him be free from doing that nameless, lawless act)

In this passage, the kings are given God's advice and commands to keep the country, to govern the people. It is explained that the ruler himself first and foremost obeys the law and refrains from committing "illegal acts." The making of erroneous and dangerous laws is equated with "a kind of marrow, a kind of lily, which is like an elephant destroying a garden of lilies."

In short, an epithet is an artistic identifier that characterizes a described event, person, object, event figuratively and emotionally. In

the work, it helps to express the writer's feelings and experiences more deeply, to show his attitude to the surrounding reality. The occurrence of many epithets in Buddhism

has not bypassed the teachings of this doctrine.

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